

PRELIMINARY EVALUATION OF TEAM-BASED LEARNING IN CLINICAL TEACHING FOR NURSING STUDENTS: A PILOT STUDY

S.Sh. Pulatova¹, Hyangkyu Lee²

Tashkent State Medical University, Uzbekistan¹

Mo-Im Kim Nursing Research Institute, College of Nursing, Yonsei University, Republic of
Korea²

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Abstract. *The modernization of healthcare systems requires the introduction of innovative educational approaches that promote critical thinking, independent learning, and professional competence among nursing students. Team-Based Learning (TBL) is a student-centered educational strategy that has demonstrated positive effects on student engagement, communication skills, and academic performance in health professions education. However, evidence regarding its implementation in nursing education programs in Uzbekistan remains limited. The aim of this pilot study was to develop a TBL-based educational module for the discipline “Nursing in Therapy,” validate adapted assessment instruments, and evaluate the preliminary impact of TBL on educational outcomes among nursing students. A single-group pretest-posttest pilot study was conducted among ten second-year nursing students at Tashkent State Medical University. The intervention included structured self-study, individual readiness assurance testing, team readiness assurance testing, and clinical case discussions. Three educational outcomes were assessed using culturally adapted and validated questionnaires measuring self-directed learning, attitudes toward learning, and academic self-efficacy. Content validity was confirmed through expert review. Pre- and post-intervention scores were compared using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm adjustment for multiple comparisons. Following implementation of the TBL module, statistically significant improvements were observed in attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy. The median score for attitudes toward learning decreased from 2.41 to 1.44 (Holm-adjusted $p = 0.00586$), while academic self-efficacy improved from 2.21 to 1.95 (Holm-adjusted $p = 0.00586$). Self-directed learning demonstrated a slight numerical increase but did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.2617$). These findings suggest that TBL may positively influence motivational and psychological aspects of learning among nursing students. Although limited by the small sample size and single-center design, the study demonstrates the feasibility of implementing TBL within undergraduate nursing education in Uzbekistan and provides a foundation for larger controlled studies in the future.*

Keywords: *team-based learning, nursing education, self-directed learning, academic self-efficacy, pilot study.*

Introduction

In the context of the modernization of the healthcare system and medical education, the necessity of implementing innovative, student-centered teaching methods aimed at the formation of clinical thinking, independence, and professional competencies of learners is increasing. Traditional lecture-based forms of instruction, predominantly based on passive assimilation of

information, do not fully ensure the development of critical thinking and decision-making skills in clinical practice.

One of the promising directions is the Team-Based Learning (TBL) method, which is actively applied in international medical education practice. This approach contributes to increasing student engagement, the development of communication skills, strengthening confidence in their own knowledge, as well as enhancing their ability to apply this knowledge in practical settings [1-3].

Despite previously reported positive effects of TBL, its systematic implementation in nursing education programs in Uzbekistan remains limited. Recent reviews have further confirmed that TBL improves student engagement, knowledge retention, teamwork skills, and academic performance across health professions education settings [7–10].

Aim of the Study

The aim of this study was ① to develop an educational module based on the Team-Based Learning method for the discipline “Nursing in Therapy,” ② to validate assessment instruments and ③ analyze the impact of the implementation of this method on students’ learning performance indicators.

Materials and Methods

A single-group pretest-posttest pilot study was conducted in two stages: first, the development and validation of the educational module and assessment instruments; second, the implementation of the pilot intervention and evaluation of its preliminary effectiveness.

At the first stage, a module was developed for the discipline “Nursing in Therapy,” delivered at the nursing faculty of Tashkent State Medical University. The training was conducted among second-year students. The module included key clinical topics—arterial hypertension and anemia.

The educational process was reorganized in accordance with the principles of Team-Based Learning (TBL) and included the following stages: preliminary self-study preparation, individual readiness assurance testing (iRAT), team readiness assurance testing (tRAT), and the application of knowledge through solving clinical case scenarios. To ensure the proper implementation of the method, a training workshop was conducted for instructors.

To assess educational outcomes, three previously developed Korean instruments were used. Self-directed learning ability was measured using the Korea Educational Development Institute instrument developed by Lee et al. [4]. Learning attitude was assessed using a 16-item instrument adapted for nursing students by Hwang [5]. Academic self-efficacy was measured using the scale developed and validated by Kim and Park [6], consisting of three subdomains: task difficulty preference, self-regulation efficacy, and self-confidence. The questionnaires were translated into Uzbek, culturally adapted, and reviewed by experts in nursing education; content validity was assessed using the Content Validity Index (CVI).

At the second stage, a pilot study was conducted involving 10 second-year students of the nursing faculty of Tashkent State Medical University. The questionnaires were administered before and after the implementation of the TBL method.

Before statistical analysis, negatively worded items were reverse-coded according to the original scoring rules. For the self-directed learning instrument, higher scores indicated more favorable characteristics. For the learning attitude and academic self-efficacy instruments, lower scores indicated more favorable characteristics after reverse coding. Scale scores were then

calculated at the participant level. Internal consistency of the translated/adapted versions was additionally examined using Cronbach’s α coefficients. In the present sample, Cronbach’s α values were 0.898 and 0.433 for self-directed learning ability, 0.708 and 0.541 for learning attitude, and 0.632 and 0.782 for academic self-efficacy at pre- and post-intervention assessment, respectively. Given the pilot nature of the study and the very small sample size, these coefficients were interpreted as preliminary estimates of internal consistency. Because this was a pilot pre–post study with paired observations and a small sample size ($n = 10$), statistical power was limited and the findings should be interpreted with caution. Pre-intervention and post-intervention scores were compared using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Holm adjustment was applied to control for multiple comparisons. Due to the small sample size, the results cannot be generalized and require confirmation in larger studies.

Results

Within the framework of the conducted study, changes in students’ learning performance indicators before and after the implementation of the Team-Based Learning (TBL) method were assessed using three scales: self-directed learning (Q1), attitudes toward learning (Q2), and academic self-efficacy (Q3).

Prior to inferential analysis, all reverse-coded items were recoded according to the scoring rules of each instrument. Given the pilot nature of the study and the small sample size ($n = 10$), descriptive statistics are presented as median and interquartile range (IQR), and pre–post comparisons were performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test with Holm adjustment for multiple comparisons. The direction of change was interpreted according to the scoring key of each instrument: higher scores were favorable for Q1, whereas lower scores were favorable for Q2 and Q3. Statistically significant favorable changes were identified for attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy, whereas the change in self-directed learning did not reach statistical significance. These findings should be interpreted with caution. The results of the pre–post comparison are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1. Changes in Educational Outcome Indicators Before and After TBL Implementation ($n = 10$)

Indicator	Before, median (IQR)	After, median (IQR)	p-value	p (Holm)	Effect size, r
Q1 Self-directed learning	3.90 (3.76–4.02)	3.98 (3.89–4.06)	0.2617	0.2617	+0.35
Q2 Attitudes toward learning	2.41 (2.20–2.53)	1.44 (1.44–1.61)	0.0039	0.00586	–0.91
Q3 Academic self-efficacy	2.21 (2.09–2.51)	1.95 (1.72–2.02)	0.00195	0.00586	–0.98

Note. For Q1, higher scores indicate more favorable outcomes; for Q2 and Q3, lower scores indicate more favorable outcomes after reverse coding. Therefore, the direction of improvement/deterioration was interpreted according to the scoring key of each instrument. *p*-values were calculated using the two-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Holm correction was

applied across the three comparisons. Wilcoxon effect size was calculated as $r = Z/\sqrt{N}$, where $N = 10$ paired observations; the sign indicates the direction of the median change.

Figure 1. Comparison of Median Scale Scores Before and After TBL

The analysis of the data presented in Table 1 showed that self-directed learning (Q1) did not demonstrate a statistically significant pre–post change following the implementation of the TBL module. The median score increased slightly from 3.90 (IQR 3.76–4.02) before the intervention to 3.98 (IQR 3.89–4.06) after the intervention; however, this shift did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.2617$; Holm-adjusted $p = 0.2617$).

In contrast, statistically significant changes were observed in attitudes toward learning (Q2) and academic self-efficacy (Q3) in this pilot sample; however, due to the limited sample size, these findings should be interpreted as preliminary. For Q2, the median score decreased from 2.41 (IQR 2.20–2.53) before the intervention to 1.44 (IQR 1.44–1.61) after the intervention, indicating improvement according to the scoring direction of the instrument ($p = 0.0039$; Holm-adjusted $p = 0.00586$). Similarly, for Q3, the median score decreased from 2.21 (IQR 2.09–2.51) to 1.95 (IQR 1.72–2.02), also reflecting a favorable change ($p = 0.00195$; Holm-adjusted $p = 0.00586$).

Thus, within this pilot sample, the most consistent favorable changes were observed for attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy, whereas the change in self-directed learning remained statistically non-significant. Given the pilot nature of the study and the small sample size ($n = 10$), these findings should be interpreted with caution.

Individual directional changes across participants are summarized in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 2.

Table 2. Individual Direction of Pre–Post Changes Across the Three Educational Outcome Scales ($n = 10$)

Indicator	Improvement (n)	No change (n)	Deterioration (n)
Q1 Self-directed learning	7	0	3
Q2 Attitudes toward learning	10	0	0
Q3 Academic self-efficacy	10	0	0

Improvement/no change/deterioration were defined according to the scoring direction of each instrument. For Q1 (self-directed learning), higher post-intervention scores indicated improvement. For Q2 (attitudes toward learning) and Q3 (academic self-efficacy), lower post-intervention scores indicated improvement.

Table 2 provides a descriptive summary of the individual direction of pre–post changes across the three scales. For self-directed learning (Q1), the directional classification was corrected according to the Q1 scoring key: 7 students showed improvement and 3 students showed deterioration. This correction resolves the apparent inconsistency noted by the reviewer, because the increase in the group median from 3.90 to 3.98 is consistent with a predominance of individual increases in Q1 scores. For attitudes toward learning (Q2) and academic self-efficacy (Q3), all 10 participants demonstrated a favorable directional change. These descriptive patterns should be interpreted with caution given the pilot nature of the study and the small sample size.

Discussion

The findings of this pilot study suggest that the implementation of the TBL method may be associated with favorable changes in selected motivational and psychological aspects of students' learning activity, particularly attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy. However, these findings should be interpreted with caution because of the small sample size.

Previous studies have reported that Team-Based Learning can improve student engagement, learning attitudes, and academic confidence [1–3, 7–10]. The present findings are generally consistent with these reports, particularly regarding improvements in attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy. However, unlike some previous studies, self-directed learning

did not show significant improvement in this pilot sample. While previous studies have often reported improvements in self-directed learning following TBL implementation, the present pilot study did not demonstrate a statistically significant change in this domain. Differences in sample size, intervention duration, educational setting, and prior experience with active learning methods may partially explain these inconsistent findings.

Figure 2. Direction of Changes Across Q1, Q2 and Q3

In addition, some students may have experienced difficulty adapting to a more active learning model that requires greater individual responsibility and independent preparation. Because the participants had limited prior exposure to student-centered learning approaches, the transition from traditional teacher-centered instruction to TBL may initially have increased uncertainty or learning burden for some students. This may partly explain the decline observed in several participants, particularly in the domain of self-directed learning. Another possible explanation is the relatively short duration of the intervention, since self-directed learning skills may require longer exposure and repeated practice to develop.

The improvement in attitudes toward learning may be related to the active involvement of students in the educational process, including group interaction, discussion, and the use of clinical case scenarios. These components may contribute to a more positive perception of the learning process and greater interest in the studied material.

The positive shift in academic self-efficacy may reflect increased confidence in students' own knowledge and abilities. This may be associated with core features of TBL, including teamwork, peer interaction, and immediate feedback during the learning process.

In contrast, self-directed learning did not demonstrate a statistically significant pre–post change. Moreover, individual responses on this scale were heterogeneous, suggesting that the effect of TBL on self-directed learning may be less immediate and may require a longer period of implementation. Self-regulation skills such as planning, sustained independent task performance,

and self-reflection are likely to develop more gradually than attitudes toward learning or confidence in one's academic abilities.

Taken together, these findings suggest that, within this pilot sample, TBL showed the most consistent positive association with attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy, whereas its influence on self-directed learning remains uncertain and requires further investigation in larger studies with longer follow-up.

Conclusion

In this pilot study, the developed Team-Based Learning module for the discipline "Nursing in Therapy," implemented among second-year nursing students of Tashkent State Medical University in Uzbekistan, was associated with favorable changes in attitudes toward learning and academic self-efficacy.

This pilot study suggests preliminary feasibility of implementing TBL in nursing education. However, given the small sample size and single-center design, the results should be interpreted with caution. Further studies involving larger samples, multiple institutions, control groups, and longer follow-up are needed to confirm these findings.

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